

Blood Bank Competency Evaluation of Interns of an Urban Medical College in South IndiaMadhuri Rao¹, Vijaya C.², Ganraj Bhat S.³, Prakash H. M.⁴¹Assistant Professor Department of Pathology, Sapthagiri Institute of Medical Sciences and Research center, Bangalore²Professor and Head, Department of Pathology, Sapthagiri Institute of Medical Sciences and Research center, Bangalore³Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Sapthagiri Institute of Medical Sciences and Research center, Bangalore⁴Professor, Department of Pathology, Karwar Institute of Medical Sciences, Karwar

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Abstract:

Introduction: National medical council introduced new regulations for internship program in 2021, making it mandatory for interns to get exposed to blood bank/ transfusion medicine training during postings in clinical departments. This is in line with other countries introducing competency-based medication education in blood bank/ transfusion medicine to train interns/ residents to have adequate knowledge and skill in ordering blood/ blood products, initiating transfusion and managing any adverse event/ complications during the procedure.

Aim: To identify the knowledge gap in the interns regarding safe transfusion practices after introduction of competency based medical education in internship training.

Material and Methods: The study was conducted in an urban medical college in South India. 150 students of the outgoing internship batch were given a Google form survey of 15 MCQs/ responses containing questions related to assessment of competency and knowledge.

Results: 101 students were included in the study based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. 84.15% of interns agreed that the education/ training received was adequate. 80.2% of interns felt competent enough to identify and manage complications. 53.46% of interns self-assessed themselves to be competent to initiate and monitor the transfusion of blood and blood products. Regarding theoretical knowledge, the average correct answers related to various topics were blood products (52.47%), blood donation (62.37%), screening/ serology (45.54%), and practical transfusion aspect (27.32%). Overall average answers related to knowledge was 58.09%.

Conclusion: The discrepancy in self-assessed competency to actual knowledge was worrisome. In the actual world, this could be catastrophic issues regarding patient safety. Interns need to understand the importance of this life-saving procedure and the limited availability of blood/ blood products. Focussed education and training with direct observation by faculty during procedures with regular/ immediate feedback could help in following National Medical Council guidelines to make the outgoing interns, an Indian Medical Graduate, who can effectively act as a physician of first contact of the community while being globally relevant.

Keywords: Blood bank, Interns, competency, CBME.

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Introduction

Blood transfusion, considered to be the first successful organ transplant is an important therapeutic intervention revolutionizing modern health care. Requests for increased usage of blood products are increasing with newer treatment methods, particularly in generalized hemorrhages, hematological as well as oncological patients, undergoing various surgical procedures. An optimal and correct use of blood products is essential and all involved, need to have a thorough training. [1] Blood transfusion, even though a frequently performed procedure, remains an

invasive procedure that should not be underestimated. It is imperative that, all staff involved in the administration of the blood products, are trained well in appropriate administration, adverse events/complications, and procedural risks. However, worldwide, training/ education in blood banking/ transfusion medicine has received little attention. Due to this, physician's knowledge is inadequate and it will have a negative impact on clinical practice. [2,3] Knowledge of outgoing interns regarding guidelines and management related to blood transfusion is critical,

as they impact patient care directly. Inappropriate blood usage and poor competency in blood transfusion could endanger patient safety. Internship training involves clinical training and conventional education in blood banking.

The need to raise the standard of training in blood banking is essential. Various studies have shown that there is a lack of standardization in both developing and developed countries and also within faculties of the same country. Several countries have scrutinized and put forth various suggestions. [4]

In India, for improvement National Medical Council (NMC), since 2019 has introduced the competency-based medical education (CBME) curriculum to train MBBS students of India on par with international standards. New regulations for internship were also introduced on 18th November 2021, as per which Blood bank/ transfusion medicine exposure via interpretation of blood grouping and saline cross matching was made compulsory as well as mandatory exposure to transfusion medicine/blood bank during postings for training in clinical departments was done. The interns are expected to order blood/ blood products, observe blood transfusion (on patients/ simulation) as well as, interpret manual blood grouping and saline cross-matching. [5].

Previously interns had minimal exposure to blood bank protocols and guidelines, as they were not made mandatory, and it is not covered in detail in Undergraduate education. [6] This study was conducted on the first outgoing internship batch after the introduction of new NMC regulations for internship, in which blood bank/ transfusion medicine skill procedures and training were made mandatory as part of Internship regulations for competency-based medical education.

Objectives: This study was done to identify the knowledge gap and self-assessment of the competency of interns concerning safe transfusion practices.

Materials and Methods

A single center MCQ self-assessment-based online survey using Google Forms was performed

amongst outgoing interns. This study was conducted in a 10-year-old medical college, in an urban setup in South India. A total of 15 questions related to self-assessment of training/ competency, blood products, blood donation, screening/serology, and bedside practices (Indications/ transfusion reactions) during blood component transfusion were put up in the Google form. 150 students of outgoing internship batch students were asked to participate in the study. Google form was shared through WhatsApp and students were asked to fill it based on their knowledge. Ethical committee clearance for the study was obtained.

Inclusion Criteria: Students of the outgoing internship batch, who followed new NMC internship guidelines (2021) and filled Google forms.

Exclusion Criteria: Students of outgoing internship batch, who completed under previous NMC internship guidelines (before 2021) and students with incomplete filled Google forms.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive analysis was done.

Results

The study included 101 out of 150 outgoing internship students, based on inclusion criteria. They were evaluated regarding the self-assessed competency/ knowledge gained during their clinical training as well as skill procedure training in transfusion medicine/ blood bank during their compulsory internship.

Assessment of competency: In questions related to self-assessment of training received in blood bank regarding their education/ training, 85/101 students agreed it to be adequate. For questions, related to the management of complications, 81/101 felt competent enough to identify and manage complications. Students, for question related to competency in initiating and monitoring transfusion of blood and blood products, 54/101, felt confident enough to do it in emergency.

Questions and answers related to self-assessment/ competency are as shown in Table: 1.

Table 1: Questions related to self-assessment/ competency

Sl no.	Self-assessment/ competency evaluation	Responses
1	The education in Blood banks is adequate for you to identify patient requirements as per guidelines, order and transfuse blood/ blood products	Strongly disagree- 9 (8.9%) Disagree-7 (6.9%) Partially agree-28 (27.7%) Agree-39 (38.6%) Strongly agree-18(17.8%)
2	How competent do you feel regarding complications related to blood and blood donor product transfusion	I can't identify complications -3(3%) I can identify complications but can't apply any treatment – 17 (16.8%) I can identify complications and I can give

		first line treatment–81 (80.2%)
3	How competent do you feel in initiating and monitoring the transfusion of blood and blood products	I don't find myself competent – 4 (4%) I can apply it by receiving support in an emergency–43 (42.6%) I have competence in this application- 54 (53.5%)

Assessment of theoretical knowledge: The students were given 12 questions related to theoretical knowledge. For questions related to theoretical knowledge, average correct answers related to various topics were - blood products

(52.47%), blood donation (62.37%), screening/serology (45.54%), and practical transfusion aspect (27.32%). Detailed answers related to knowledge are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Questions related to knowledge

Sl no.	Question	Appropriately answered
	Blood products	
4	Life span of Platelets	44/101
5	Blood is stored at a temperature of	62/101
	Blood donation	
6	How often can a donor give blood?	52/101
7	Patients with controlled Diabetes mellitus and hypertension can donate blood	74/101
	Screening/ serology	
8	Cross matching is not compulsory if both donor and recipient have same blood group	89/101
9	Infectious diseases screened in India (can select more than one)	16/101
10	Saline suspension of red cells is used in cross matching in blood bank to	33/101
	Practical transfusion aspects	
11	Indications of packed red cells transfusion are (can select more than one)	38/101
12	After receiving blood bag from blood bank, transfusion should be started	7/101
13	Blood transfusion should be completed within 4 hours to prevent	18/101
14	Which actions can be performed to prevent febrile non hemolytic transfusion reaction	14/101
15	If signs and symptoms of transfusion reactions are noted, we should	61/101

Discussion

The knowledge related to blood banking, and its theoretical and practical contexts varies amongst the interns within the between batches. This will lead to inappropriate use of blood as well as increased risk of adverse events due to transfusion reactions, impacting the financial condition of the patient. [6] Residents and interns form the backbone of hospital services. Managing blood products, without proper blood banking training can be a nightmarish experience for all involved. [7] In the 2020 Serious Hazards of Transfusion report, approximately 30.7% of incorrect blood component transfusion errors occurred at blood ordering. [8]

In a study by Kupesiz FT et al, 2% of intern students under study, strongly agreed to have adequate education to be competent in the blood bank, while in our study 17.8% of students evaluated strongly agreed. 15.8% of students in our study, disagreed to strongly disagree about the lack of adequate education in blood banks, while in the study by Kupesiz FT et al, it was 65%. [4]

In our study, a total of 58.09% of interns had poor knowledge, compared to 41.5% in residents in a

study by Ray GK et al, 54.3% of residents in a study by Haspel RL et al [9], and 50.3% among cancer physicians in a study by Ddhungu H et al. [10] When the student's ability to recognize transfusion-related complications was evaluated, in our study, 3% of students were unsure, while in a study by Kupesiz FT et al, 30% of students did not express confidence in identifying complications. In our study, students' self-evaluation of competency of initiating and monitoring of transfusion, 53.5% of students felt competent, while in a study by Kupesiz FT et al, 7% of students felt competent. [4]

CBME was implemented with the core idea of CBME with its implementation has put forth multiple challenges at the faculty level as well as students level. It stresses individualized and flexible learning plans, independent of time. The faculty supervision is switched to active direct observation and immediate feedback from previously passive observation. The clinical department's teaching of CBME has increased as they need to document observations and fill evaluation forms, in addition to already existing patient care duty as well as administration work. Inadequate/overburdened faculty could affect the implementation of CBME effectively, thereby

affecting student's training, in blood bank/transfusion medicine evaluation. [11] Effective ideas in implementing CBME for residents/ interns include documenting students' reports of audit, and practicing clinical guidelines and reports through reflective critique. This could help in the demonstration of understanding of the importance of adequate utilization of blood supplies, following safety guidelines, quality issues as well as modification of practice to meet specific patient needs in different clinical contexts. Further on, as time progresses, students need to understand that it is essential to monitor transfusion practices and make it more clinical evidence-based. [11,12] At the faculty level, reducing burden of implementing CBME can be done through incentives for faculty members to take on CBME roles (eg: Financial remuneration, promotion or credit towards tenure), using skill labs for simulation based learning and distribute across all faculty members, the responsibility of direct observation and feedback. [11] The overall students' theoretical knowledge needs to be assessed and properly addressed. In our study, compared to student's self-assessment of competency, theoretical knowledge assessment appeared to be low. This could pose challenges in blood transfusion when the students enter residency or work in emergency departments, where the essential requirement is to avoid wastage of precious resources, which could occur through ordering unnecessary transfusions, unable to manage complications. Studies have shown that experienced clinicians are also unfamiliar with current practice guidelines for blood and blood product transfusion. Because of this, studies have repeatedly stressed the need for providing focused education in blood banking and transfusion practices, as the new graduates are yet to realize that they are not well equipped for transfusion. [4,12]

Further on, as time progresses, students need to understand that it is essential to monitor transfusion practices and make it more clinical evidence-based. Regarding the adequacy of transfusion medicine education and opportunities for intervention, educators in studies have considered two weeks as the minimum contact time up to a month. Studies have shown that experienced clinicians are also unfamiliar with current practice guidelines for blood and blood product transfusion. Regular audits and periodic exposure to transfusion medicine training have been known to be very useful in the optimal utilization of blood components. Formation of a Hospital transfusion committee with students attending it as part of the training will help in improving blood utilization [2,12-14] The main limitation of the present study was, it was limited to a single center survey. A larger multicentric survey with a much wider

variety of competency evaluation and knowledge assessment along with simulation-based assessment would be essential to understand the knowledge gap all over the country. Understanding this, essential modifications can be made in the internship training or modification in the post-graduate curriculum, which would go a long way in making safe blood transfusion, a lifesaving management.

Conclusion

The transfusion medicine/ blood banking curriculum is barely covered in the UG curriculum and during the internship, training is insufficient.

NMC in its PG CBME curriculum revision could stress upon the importance of providing focused education in blood banking in the first year of residency and provide competency and proper guidelines for assessment. Also, we need to impress upon the interns about being competent in blood banking and transfusion practices, as these are lifesaving procedures and if not properly trained, could become life-threatening procedures.

This research work was approved by Ethical committee of Sapthagiri Institute of Medical Sciences and Research center, Bangalore

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